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Diving into Extended Phase Graph-based Deep Learning for accurate T_2 mapping with PENGUIN

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Synopsis

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Model-based deep learning approaches have shown promising results to accelerate T_2 relaxometry, but most adopt a pure exponential curve to model the signal, which does not account for indirect and stimulated echoes. A Phase graph sigNal and Gradients QUantitative Inference MachiNe (PENGUIN) is proposed, which implements a dictionary of pre-calculated echo-modulation curves following the Extended Phase Graph (EPG) formulation and respective gradients as the inputs of a Recurrent Inference Machine to perform accurate T_2 mapping from the reconstructed images. PENGUIN is 25-fold faster than a pattern recognition approach with a T_2 dictionary step of 2 ms.

Introduction

Quantitative Magnetic Resonance Imaging often suffers from time-consuming parameter fitting operations, preventing its use in routine clinical evaluation. A new class of deep learning frameworks, called model-based deep learning nets, incorporate the MR signal model into the learning process to estimate parametric maps of the tissues, alleviating the need for a large number of training datasets and further pushing acceleration rates [1]. However, most of the previously proposed methods have employed a pure exponential curve to model the MR signal [2,3], which does not account for stimulated or indirect echoes, or inhomogeneity of the B_1 field. Here, the Phase graph sigNals and Gradients QUantitative Inference machiNe (PENGUIN) method is proposed, which adapts the Recurrent Inference Machine (RIM) implemented by Sabidussi et al. [3] (model-based method), to perform T_2 mapping of grey and white matter regions with a more accurate signal model based on the Extended Phase Graphs (EPG) concept [4], while also attempting to estimate the effective B_1 field to improve the T_2 map estimate. In addition to the new signal model, a key difference between PENGUIN and RIM is that an efficient dictionary implementation is used to obtain the forward signal model and corresponding gradients to speed up the estimation.

Methods

All methods were implemented with a signal model based on the EPG concept, following a multi echo spin-echo (ME-SE) acquisition sequence, with 32 echoes, $TE=10:10:320$ ms and flip angle (FA) = [180°, 160°, ... 160°], by modifying the code by Sabidussi et al [3]. A dictionary of echo-modulation curves (EMC) with the EPG formulation and corresponding gradients was built for $T_2 = 0:1:2000$ ms, $B_1 = 0:6:0.01:1:4$, and $T_1 = 1000$ ms.

Pattern-recognition approach: A state-of-the-art pattern-recognition approach was implemented by looping through each pixel of the reconstructed images and attributing to it the T_2 value of the dictionary whose EMC maximized its inner product with the measured signal of that pixel.

PENGUIN: PENGUIN was implemented according to the configuration in Figure 1. At each optimization step, the network performs $J=6$ inference steps to obtain 6 estimates of the parametric maps $\hat{\mathbf{p}}=[PD, T_2, B_1]$, where PD is a tissue-dependent normalization constant, including the proton density. The loss function was given by:

$$\Lambda^{total} = \frac{1}{J} \sum_{j=1}^J \left(\sum (\mathbf{p} - \hat{\mathbf{p}}_j)^2 \right).$$

PENGUIN finds the maximum a posteriori estimate of the signal \mathbf{m} , from which the negative log-likelihood function $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{m}|\mathbf{p})$ can be defined, while implicitly learning prior information. At each inference step, the network receives the parametric maps $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_j$, the gradient of the negative log-likelihood function $\nabla_{\mathbf{p}_j} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{m}|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_j)$ and two vectors of memory states \mathbf{h}_1^j and \mathbf{h}_2^j as input, and outputs the incremental update to the maps, $\Delta \hat{\mathbf{p}}_j$, and the updated vectors of memory states \mathbf{h}_{j+1}^1 and \mathbf{h}_{j+1}^2 . During evaluation, PENGUIN uses the dictionary to speed up the calculation of $\hat{\mathbf{m}}_j$ and $\nabla_{\mathbf{p}_j} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{m}|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_j)$ compared to the reference RIM implementation.

PENGUIN and RIM networks were implemented with PyTorch 1.10.2, trained on a NVIDIA TESLA P100 GPU, and tested on an Intel Core i7 2.8 GHz CPU. All networks were trained using the Adam optimizer, a learning-rate of 0.005, and 72 patches per minibatch, for a total of 120 epochs.

Simulated Data: Networks were fully trained with simulated data from ten BrainWeb's discrete anatomical images [5]. Each 3D image was randomly split into 7200 2D patches, from which a set of ground truth \mathbf{p} maps and corresponding T_2 weighted images \mathbf{m} were simulated with the EPG implementation, following the scheme in Figure 2. Two additional simulated images were created to test the networks, following the same protocol but considering the full slice (Figure 3).

In vivo Data: PENGUIN was tested and compared to the pattern recognition method on *in vivo* images of a healthy subject previously acquired in a Philips Achieva 3T scanner with the ME-SE sequence detailed above, imaging 6 slices with spatial resolution of $1.6 \times 1.6 \times 4.0$ mm³, field-of-view 250×250 mm², and repetition time of 4 s.

Results

PENGUIN can estimate a 320×320 pixel map in 4.16 ± 0.10 s, 380-fold faster than the RIM implemented with the EPG signal model while achieving the same accuracy (Figure 4), and 465-fold faster than the pattern recognition approach. Even when considering the latter approach with a coarser dictionary built with $T_2=0:2:300$ ms, PENGUIN is 25 times faster. The T_2 maps estimated in the simulated images prove PENGUIN is capable of estimating known T_2 values, albeit with less accuracy than the pattern recognition approach. The T_2 maps estimated with PENGUIN in the *in vivo* images (Figure 5) have a maximum median difference of 2.8 ms in the brain parenchyma compared to those obtained with the pattern recognition approach, with a larger error in the grey matter region.

Conclusions

PENGUIN provides a faster and reliable alternative to estimate T_2 maps, by combining the advantages of the RIM (low overfitting and ability to learn the inference process) and the pattern recognition approach (use of pre-calculated dictionaries with the signal evolution and its derivatives).

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Figures

Figure 1: PENGUIN configuration drawn for inference step j . The current map estimate $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_j$ is used to obtain the weighted images $\hat{\mathbf{m}}_j$ and the gradients $\nabla_{\mathbf{p}_j} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{m}|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_j)$ from the dictionary, which are concatenated with $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_j$ along the channel dimension as input to the network, outputting the update $\Delta \hat{\mathbf{p}}_j$ to obtain $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{j+1}$. RIM shares this configuration without the use of dictionaries.

Figure 2: Protocol for generating training data. Each brain model is split into 40×40 patches. Ground truth PD and T_2 are taken from a normal distribution, centered in the expected PD and T_2 for each tissue [3], to mimic inter-subject variability, and submitted to another normal distribution to induce intra-tissue variability. B_1 maps are simulated from a normal function trimmed according to the patch location, with maximum intensity I^{B_1} , mean μ^{B_1} and variance σ^{B_1} . T_2 weighted images are generated by applying the EPG forward model.

Figure 3: T_2 maps estimated on simulated images with distinct B_1 maps, with the pattern recognition approach and PENGUIN, and difference map between them and the ground-truth. The normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) was calculated on the brain parenchyma for both methods.

Figure 4: T_2 maps estimated with the pattern recognition approach, the RIM implemented with the EPG model, and with PENGUIN (top), and difference maps between the deep learning methods and the pattern recognition method (bottom). PENGUIN and RIM present similar accuracies compared to the standard dictionary approach. However, PENGUIN (4.16 ± 0.10 s) is 380 times faster than RIM (1578 ± 82 s) and 465 times faster than the pattern recognition approach (1931 ± 130 s).

Figure 5: (Left) T_2 maps estimated from *in vivo* weighted images, each column corresponding to a different slice, with the pattern recognition approach with 1 ms T_2 dictionary step (top) and with PENGUIN (middle), and difference map between them (bottom). The median error (in ms) was calculated in the brain parenchyma region, excluding the CSF. (Right) Estimated T_2 values with both methods alongside two horizontal profiles indicated in the slices.